

MOZART - LIFE AND WORKS

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Annotation: Mozart is considered one of the geniuses of the world of music. This article discusses Mozart's life and achievements.

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INTRODUCTION

The description of Mozart's youth is replete with details that we do not find in the biographies of other composers. His musical talent showed up so early and so brightly that it involuntarily drew attention to itself. It is known, for example, according to the testimony of the court trumpeter Shachtner and Anna Maria Mozart, that four years old Mozart had already written a concerto and that he could not hear the sound of the trumpet without physical irritation. In 1761, as a five-year-old child, he took part in the choir at a performance at the Salzburg University of Liederspiel Eberlin of Sigismund, King of Hungary.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In 1762, six-year-old Mozart, with his eleven-year-old sister, went under the auspices of his father on a concert tour, first to Munich and then to Vienna. Further, stories are well known about how, with his magnificent organ playing, he delighted the monks of the monastery of Ips, and with his perfect piano playing, the princesses, and especially Marie Antoinette. It is also mentioned that many beautiful poems were written in honor of the wonderful child. The success of this trip prompted my father to undertake something new the following year - to Paris. At the same time, stops were made along the way, when visiting princely courts, residences, etc. In Mainz and Frankfurt, they gave concerts of outstanding success, visited Koblenz, Aachen and Brussels, and finally, on November 18, 1763, arrived in Paris. Here they met the patronage of Baron Grimm, played at the royal court, in front of the Marquise Pompadour, and gave two of their own concerts with brilliant success. In Paris, for the first time, four violin sonatas of the young Mozart appeared in print, of which two were dedicated to Princess Victoria of France and two to Countess Tessa. From here they went to London, where they played at the royal court and where the

Kapellmeister J.K. Bach, the son of Johann Sebastian, performed several Mozart gizmos.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During this period of time, Mozart's skill in improvising, transposing to the most distant scales, accompanying from the sheet was decidedly incomprehensible. In England, he wrote six more violin sonatas dedicated to Queen Sophia-Charlotte; here, under his direction, small symphonies written by him were performed. From London they went to The Hague, at the invitation of the Princess of Nassau, to whom Mozart dedicated the next six sonatas. In Lille, Mozart fell seriously ill almost at the same time as his sister Marianne, and both lay in The Hague for about four months, to the great despair of their father. Upon recovery, they again visited Paris, where Grimm was delighted with the successes of Mozart, and then visited Bern, Dijon, Zurich, Ulm and Munich, and finally, after a three-year absence, returned to Salzburg at the end of November 1766 [2].

Here, as a ten-year-old boy, Mozart wrote his first oratorio (Mark the Evangelist). After a year of intensive studies, he went to Vienna. The smallpox epidemic forced them to move to Olmutz, which, however, did not save the children from chickenpox. Returning to Vienna, they played at the court of Emperor Joseph II, although they did not give their own concert. Being slandered and suspected that the true author of his works is his father, the young composer refuted the slander through a brilliant public improvisation on the topics indicated to him. At the suggestion of the king, Mozart wrote his first opera, *La finta semplice* (now called *Apollo and Hyacinth*), which, due to intrigues, did not hit the Vienna stage, was first presented in Salzburg (1769). For 12 years, Mozart led the performance of his "Solemn Mass", in honor of the illumination of the church of the orphanage. A year later, he was elected the Archbishop's accompanist, shortly before his trip to Italy with his father.

Returning to Salzburg in March 1771, Mozart wrote the oratorio "The Liberation of Betulia", and in the autumn of that year he was again in Milan, where he wrote the serenade "Ascanius in Alba", in honor of the marriage of Archduke Ferdinand to Princess Beatrice of Modena. This work completely eclipsed Hass's opera "Ruggiero" on the stage. His next opera is *The Dream of Scipio*, dedicated to the successor of the deceased Archbishop of Salzburg, Count Hieronymus von Colloredo (1772). In December 1772, Mozart again visited Milan, where he staged the opera *Lucius Sulla*. In later years he composed symphonies, masses, concertos and concert music. In 1775, the opera *The Imaginary Gardener*

ordered by him was staged in Munich with outstanding success. Soon after, his opera *The Shepherd King* was given in honor of the stay of Archduke Maximilian. Despite all these successes, Mozart did not have a solid place, and his father began to think again about the tour. The archbishop, however, refused leave, after which Mozart resigned. This time he went on a journey with his mother, passing through Munich, Augsburg and Mannheim, although here his artistic trip was not successful. In addition, Mozart fell in love with the singer Alois Weber in Mannheim, and only with difficulty could they tear him away from this hobby. Finally arriving in Paris, he had artistic satisfaction after performing one of his symphonies in the Concert spirituel. But here he also experienced grief: his mother died (1778). Deeply distressed, having not achieved his goal, he returned to Salzburg, where he was forced to again take the same place under the archbishop [3].

In 1779 Mozart was appointed court organist here. In 1781, he wrote the opera *Idomeneo* on a new order, with which the classical direction of his further works begins. Shortly thereafter, he finally broke off his relationship with the archbishop and moved to Vienna. For some time, Mozart remained without a place here, until in 1789 he was appointed court composer, with a content of 800 florins. But on the other hand, he had the opportunity to perform his great works, which he took advantage of. At the suggestion of the king, he wrote the vaudeville "*The Abduction from the Seraglio*", and he was put on stage by order of the king, despite the intrigues (1781). In the same year, Mozart married Constance Weber, the sister of his first love interest [4].

In 1785, he created the opera *The Marriage of Figaro*, which, due to its poor performance by the Italians, almost failed on the Vienna stage, but was magnificently transmitted in Prague. In 1787, his *Don Giovanni* appeared, staged first in Prague, and then in Vienna, where the opera again failed. In general, misfortune haunted the brilliant Mozart in Vienna, and his works remained in the shadows, yielding to secondary compositions. In 1789, Mozart left Vienna and, accompanied by Count Lichnowsky, visited Berlin, played at the court in Dresden, Leipzig and, finally, in Potsdam before Frederick II, who appointed him the place of the first Kapellmeister with a salary of 3,000 thalers, but here Mozart's Austrian patriotism triumphed and became a hindrance to him accepting the proposed place. By order of the Austrian king, he composed the following opera, "*Thus do all (women)*" (1790). In the last year of his life, he wrote two operas: *The Mercy of Titus* for Prague, in honor of the coronation of Leopold II (September 6, 1791) and *The Magic Flute* for Vienna (September 30,

1791). His last creation was a requiem, which gave rise to the well-known fantastic story about the death of Mozart due to poisoning by his rival, the composer Salieri. This theme inspired A. S. Pushkin to create a "little tragedy" "Mozart and Salieri". Mozart's burial was very miserable: he was even buried in a common grave, so to this day the exact location of his remains is unknown. In 1859, a monument was erected to him in this cemetery (St. Mark). In 1841, a magnificent monument was erected in his honor in Salzburg [5].

CONCLUSION

In his amazing work, Mozart was fluent in musical means and forms. His personality always contains the charm of purity, intimacy and charm. His humor is less vivid than that of Haydn, and the harsh grandeur of Beethoven is completely alien to him. His style is a combination of happy Italian melody with German depth and positivity. Related features are inherent in Schubert and Mendelssohn, especially in the sense of the fecundity of their work and the short duration of their lives. Mozart's composing significance is undoubtedly global: in all kinds of music, he made a major step forward and all his works are clothed with unfading beauty. The reformist spirit of Gluck lived in him, which forced him to create unshakable types in the field of the past and modern times. If the external musical environment of his works now forces them to be evaluated from a historical point of view, then in terms of their internal content and their inspired thoughts, they still have not become outdated.

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